

Additional file 2: Figure with estimated parameters from the experimental data of all conditions for each combination of sensitivity functions by adding muscle activation and acceleration feedback in the fitted model.

Parameter values are given with standard error of the mean (SEM) of 10 conditions (0.5, 1, 2, 4 and 8 degrees peak-to-peak amplitude with eyes open (EO) and eyes closed (EC)). BS: body sway, T: ankle torque, MA: muscle activation, ACT: activation dynamics, K_a: acceleration feedback.